

WWF

FR

2023

Marine Protected Areas Odyssey
North-east Coast of Ibiza-Tagomago
Marine Reserve

September 2023

Marine Protected Areas Odyssey – Report of the 2023 mission in the North- east Coast of Ibiza-Tagomago Marine Reserve

March 2024

FOREWORD

Context, funding and partners: This study report is part of the “The Odyssey of MPAs in the Mediterranean” program, developed by WWF-France and realized in partnership with Septentrion Environnement (SE). This report presents the actions undertaken and results of the field mission done in October–November 2023, carried out in the territory and with the partnership of the “Reserva marina de la costa noreste de Ibiza–Tagomago” or North–east Coast of Ibiza–Tagomago Marine Reserve. The project is co-funded by the sponsorship of the company CMA–CGM.

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Citation : “ Richaume J., Nunez L., Ody, D., Estaque T., Fargetton M., Ody A., Personnic S., Cheminée A., 2024. Marine Protected Areas Odyssey (MPA Odyssey) – Report of the 2023 mission in the Northeast coast marine reserve of Ibiza – Tagomago. Septentrion publ., 41p. ”.

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1. Introduction

This study is part of the Marine Protected Areas Odyssey programme, directed by WWF-France in the Mediterranean. The MPA Odyssey is a multi-year scientific field expedition, carried out aboard the Blue Panda, and aimed at strengthening the impact of MMI advocacy so that 30% of the Mediterranean is protected and in the process of recovery and that 3% is completely protected (strong protection).

This report presents the actions undertaken and results of the field mission done in October and November 2023, carried out on the coast of the North-east Coast of Ibiza-Tagomago Marine Reserve, with in partnership with its managers and the assistance of WWF Spain.

The main objective of this mission was to collect data through visual censuses carried out underwater aimed at describing and analysing the state of the fish assemblages (Harmelin-Vivien et al., 1985) within the Tagomago reserve: (1) all firstly, in order to assess the level of protection offered by the MPA, sites inside and outside the no-take zones were sampled; (2) in addition, these data were collected to update data on particular sites and/or those that are likely to be integrated into strong protection zones in the future; Furthermore, (3) we sought to put these data into perspective with data from other MPAs in the Mediterranean (Harmelin-Vivien et al., 2008).

2. Mission Procedure

The team was made up of 6 scientific divers who carried out the underwater visual census, a mission leader, a scientific supervisor and 3 crew members.

Scientific team

Adrien CHEMINEE - Septentrion Environment – Scientific supervision, scientific diver.

Tristan ESTAQUE – Septentrion Environnement – Scientific diver.

Margaux FARGETTON – Septentrion Environnement – Scientific diver.

Lucie NUNEZ – Septentrion Environnement – Scientific diver.

Denis ODY – WWF France – Mission leader, surface safety, scientific diver.

Anouck ODY – Septentrion Environnement – Scientific diver.

Sébastien PERSONNIC – Septentrion Environnement – Scientific diver.

Justine RICHAUME – Septentrion Environnement – Scientific diver.

Blue Panda crew members

Nicolas BIN – Captain

Louis du PETIT THOUARS – Sailor

Hugo PIERRE – Sailor

Pauline FAUGERES – Sailor

3. Materials and Methods

3.1. Location and Presentation of Sampling areas and Sites

During the mission, **32 sites** spread over **6 areas** were sampled (Fig. 1). The 32 sites studied were selected on the basis of available data concerning the description of biotopes and biocenoses: along the coastline, the selected sites had to present habitats with the following characteristics: sublittoral rock that can be partially covered (< 50%) of *P. oceanica* meadows, located between 7 and 15 meters deep. We targeted this habitat because it is known to be a representative case study to quantify the response of fish assemblages to the level of protection (Garcia-Rubies and Zabala, 1990). However, some variations in habitat characteristics remained, sometimes showing shallower rocky bottoms (4–5 m) or mixed areas with a low percentage of *Posidonia oceanica* meadow cover on rock. Sites and their characteristics are listed in Appendix A1 and in the result full database (available upon request).

The Marine Reserve of the Northeast coast of Ibiza-Tagomago (“**Tagomago MPA**” in the text below) (BOIB nº157, of December 15, 2018), occupies an area of 3756 ha, within which an Integral Reserve occupies 268.7 ha. Studied sites were a priori grouped into six areas that displayed homogeneity in terms of both geomorphological and fishing regulation characteristics : the **areas** we studied were located in the north-east part of Ibiza and were named as follows : **North Outside MPA, North MPA, Integral Reserve, Tagomago Island, South MPA** and **South Outside MPA** (Fig. 1).

In the partially protected zone only certain minor professional fishing gear are allowed: boats registered to fishing guilds can fish of Ibiza and Sant Antoni de Portmany. Recreational surface fishing and recreational shellfishing are allowed, although the only rigging allowed are the steering wheel/jigging and the surface troller. In all cases, the lines must be manual or with reel rod. Diving is allowed with a permit only. An authorization of the General Directorate of Fisheries is required for the development of activities with scientific or communication purposes.

In the integral reserve, located around the slab since Figueral, the measures are more restrictive: fishing activity is prohibited, both professional and recreational, as well as any type of underwater activity without prior authorization from administration.

Figure 1. Map of 32 sites sampled during the MPA Odyssey mission in Ibiza – Tagomago MPA. Each site is represented by a dot and number (colors indicate the area to which each site belongs to). The Tagomago MPA currently includes an Integral Reserve (red squared, i.e. fully protected) and a partially protected zone (displayed in dark blue). A future enlargement of the MPA (displayed in light blue) is currently under consideration by authorities.

Marine habitats within the MPA include *Posidonia oceanica* meadows, *Cymodocea nodosa* meadows, communities of photophilic algae and communities of sciaphilic algae linked to rocky bottoms, fine sand communities, coarse and medium sands in which beds of rhodoliths or coralligenous ecosystem can be found. Managers evoke that some apex-predators are low in abundance and size, such as large coastal predators (common grouper *Epinephelus marginatus*, *Dentex dentex* or *Scorpaena scrofa*). Management objectives displayed include to produce an increase in commercial fish populations within the marine reserve and its surroundings, which would favor the artisanal fishing sector of Ibiza and the economic activities related to recreational fishing, diving and snorkeling. Therefore, managers highlight the need to regulate the authorized activities so that they are practiced in a way compatible with conservation and resource sustainability (Arpa Vila et al., 2020).

3.2. Underwater Dive Inventory Protocols

As regards the sampling method, we used underwater visual census (UVC) of fish assemblages, with a transect of 25 m long by 5 m wide as the sampling unit. The abundance of each fish species was counted, or estimated for large groups, and their

individual size estimated in increments of 2 cm (for individuals smaller than 30 cm), or 6 cm (for larger ones) (Harmelin-Vivien et al., 2008, 1985). A single pass per transect was carried out, focusing on necto-benthic species (sparids, wrasses, serranids, etc.) (Harmelin, 1987) which are the most sensitive to the level of protection (Garcia-Rubies and Zabala, 1990). Cryptic species were not counted.

Among the MPA, within each site, the sampling units (n = 6 transects) were peaked out according to a stratified random sampling design, targeting the habitat described above, in an average depth range of 7 to 15 meters, and in a manner to limit the percentage of seagrass coverage (maximum of 50%, wherever possible).

3.3. Data Processing and Analysis

3.3.1. Fish assemblage descriptors

Data processing was carried out using visual inventory data (species, abundance and size of fish) acquired by scientific divers within the **192** transects carried out on the **32** sites, grouped into **6** areas. **Descriptive variables of fish assemblages** were extracted from the raw data and included species occurrence (proportion of transects where a species was present), species overall dominance (proportion of individuals of a given species out of the number counted for all species combined), total abundance and total biomass, species richness, abundance and relative biomass by species (population composition), as well as abundance by size classes for certain species. Biomass was calculated from the abundance and size of individuals per species using commonly used size-biomass conversion factors for fishes dwelling in the infralittoral rocky reef biocenosis (Thibaut et al., 2017).

After examining the occurrence of species, the gregarious species (*C. chromis*, *Spicara* spp., *B. boops* and *Atherina* spp.), which were very abundant on the majority of transects, were subsequently removed from the data to perform the following analyzes to prevent masking the signal of less abundant species. Among observed species (Appendix A2), Mediterranean species commonly targeted by fishing were also examined more closely. We used a standard list of targeted species for the Mediterranean which included *D. annularis*, *D. dentex*, *D. puntazzo*, *D. sargus*, *D. vulgaris*, *C. julis*, *L. merula*, *L. viridis*, *M. surmuletus*, *S. scribea*, *S. salpa*, *S. aurata* and *O. melanura* (Appendix A3).

The **explanatory variables** of the sampling design were the area (fixed factor with 6 modalities: North Outside MPA, North MPA, Integral Reserve, Tagomago Island, South MPA and South Outside MPA) and the site (factor nested in area, with 32 modalities) (see Fig. 1). Differences in abundance and biomass between areas were tested statistically. Since the data does not have a normal distribution and the homogeneity of variances is not respected, we performed a Kruskal-Wallis test (non-parametric test similar to Anova). The pairwise differences between the different modalities of the "Area" factor were then tested using a post-hoc test by Siegel and Castellán, adapted to the Kruskal-Wallis test.

On the other hand, we used a “**gradient analysis**”, displaying for each transect the -log of the ratio of abundance divided by biomass, for fished species. This descriptor makes it possible to check whether, at constant abundance, the fish are larger or smaller in one area or another. This -log ratio increases when the biomass increases at constant abundance, which is the case when the individuals are larger. Such a “gradient” analysis was carried out by considering a South–Center gradient and a North–Center gradient on either side of the center of the Integral Reserve. Sites from the South Outside MPA area, South MPA and Tagomago Island areas (sites 1 to 9, and 29 to 32) formed the South–Center gradient, and sites from the Integral Reserve, North MPA and North Outside MPA areas (sites 10 to 28) formed the North–Center gradient. Regression lines were used to present the general tendency for the South–Center gradient and North–Center gradient.

Finally, an **analysis of the ratio of total abundance** inside the NTZs (No–Take zones) *versus* outside the NTZ (ONTZs) **and of the biomass** inside the NTZs *versus* outside the NTZs (ONTZs) allowed us to compare the effectiveness of the protections put in place in the marine protected areas studied within the framework of the BIOMEX project (Harmelin–Vivien et al., 2008) and those of the MPA Odyssey project. For Tagomago MPA, the abundance and biomass ratios were made respectively between Integral Reserve *versus* outside unprotected areas and on the other hand between the partially protected zone of the Tagomago MPA *versus* outside unprotected areas. A comparison with the average ratios of respectively abundance and biomass between unprotected areas and NTZs found in other Mediterranean MPAs (Giakoumi et al., 2017) also made it possible to position the average observed in the MPA studied here.

All figures and descriptive and inferential statistics were produced with R Studio software v.4.0.5 (R Core Team, 2017).

3.3.2. Scenarios of stronger protection

As an improvement of the current management plan and based on the MPA’s Odyssey program results, we proposed alongside our field data analysis a new management scenario with the creation of larger No–Take Zones (NTZ) and Professional Fishing Reserved Areas (PFRAs) (see Fig. 22 in the discussion), where recreational fishing is prohibited, and we compared the fish “Production” that would be expected for this scenario *versus* the current situation, for the same superficies.

If we consider for example a given zone, with a mean *in situ* biomass of fish, the “Production” is what is expected to be produced and exported annually per unit of surface (ha), through natural growth and reproduction of these fish individuals. The Production is directly and positively correlated with the “*in situ* Biomass”: previous studies from the BIOMEX program (Harmelin–Vivien et al., 2008), obtained in 6 mediterranean model MPAs, demonstrated that the “Production/*in situ* Biomass” ratio is typically about 0.315 and 0.366 in average for sites located respectively inside or outside no–take zones. This ratio [Production]/[*in situ* Biomass] depends also on the proportion of the different categories of fish in the assemblage. Knowing the *in-situ* biomass of a given zone, and using these ratios, it is consequently possible to evaluate the production

expected from this given zone under various scenarios : the difference of production between a scenario where the zone becomes a NTZ or remains in the current not-protected situation can be considered as the “revenues of a capital” and also as what is available for fishing around the NTZ.

The potential “*in situ* biomasses” of the new NTZ in the present scenario have been calculated with the *in situ* biomasses observed in this study multiplied by the average ratio of [biomass inside]/[outside NTZs] known from 24 mediterranean MPAs (Giakoumi et al., 2017). The value of this ratio is x2.3 and should be considered as rather conservative since we had higher values in BIOMEX (x5.6 in average and up to x9.7; Harmelin-Vivien et al., 2008) and in MPAs Odyssey data in Corsica in 2022 (x4.5; Estaque et al., 2023).

We performed the same calculation if designing a Professional Fishing Reserved Areas surrounding the NTZ (PFRA): we took into account the increase of “*In situ* Biomass” in this Professional Fishing Reserved Areas (PFRA) resulting from prohibiting recreational fishing. We used data from a similar design in Corsica (Estaque et al. 2023) where the *in situ* biomasses in the PFRA are 2.7 and 3.7 times higher than in open areas. We used x2 as a conservative estimate.

In summary, we calculated estimates of:

- The **current production** of the entire zone before setting up any NTZ or PFRA;
- Its **potential production** increased by the exedentary production resulting from the setting up of the NTZ (i.e. production available around the NTZ once protected *versus* production available when not protected), while the rest of the zone remains open to all type of fishing ;
- Its **potential production** increased by the two exedentary productions resulting (a) from the setting up of the **NTZ** and (b) resulting from the setting up of the surrounding **PFRA**.

4. Results

4.1. Sampling and Key Quantitative Properties of Teleostean Communities

4.1.1 Occurrence Frequency, Dominance, and Species Richness

In terms of occurrence, including gregarious species, *Coris julis* was the most regularly observed species (present on 97% of transects) followed by *Thalassoma pavo* (95 %), *Serranus scriba* (94%), *Symphodus tinca* (93 %), *Diplodus vulgaris* (89%), and *Chromis chromis* (80%) (Fig. 2). It is interesting to note that both *Coris julis* and *Thalassoma pavo* were observed on almost all of the transects. Among sea breams, *Diplodus vulgaris* was the most regularly observed species (89%), followed by *Diplodus sargus* (58%), *Diplodus annularis* (40%) and *Diplodus puntazzo* (24%).

In terms of dominance, the most abundant species recorded was *Thalassoma pavo* (Fig. 3), whose numbers represented 18% of all fish counted, followed by *D. vulgaris* (16%), *S. salpa* (14%), *C. julis* (11%), *S. tinca* (10.5%) and *O. melanura* (8%).

The species richness per transect (number of species) was on average 10.5 taxa (considering all sites). Species richness per transect averaged per site varied, from 5.5 taxa for site 29 (in the South Outside MPA area) to 13.5 taxa for site 14 (in the North MPA area) (Fig. 4). Certain species have been rarely observed and only on a few specific sites. Notably, mottled groupers (*Mycteroperca rubra*) were observed only in the site 12 (North MPA area) and the site 21 (North Outside MPA area). White trevally (*Pseudocaranx dentex*) was observed only in South Outside MPA area, and golden groupers (*Epinephelus costae*) were only observed in the Integral Reserve and the North MPA area (sites 10 and 12 respectively). *Diplodus cervinus* was only observed in the North MPA area (site 13). *Scorpaena scrofa* were only observed in the integral reserve (site 10) and in the North MPA area (site 12).

Globally, the total cumulated species richness, over all areas, was 40 taxa (Appendix A2), and ranged from 32 taxa cumulated for the North Outside MPA area to 28 taxa cumulated for the South Outside MPA area. Finally, considering the averages of species richness per transect by area, it varied from 9 taxa per transect for the North Outside MPA area to 12 for the Tagomago and North MPA areas (Fig. 5).

Figure 2. Frequency of occurrence of species observed during the mission within the North-east Coast of Ibiza-Tagomago Marine Reserve, (on all transects all sites combined).

Figure 3. Overall dominance of species observed during the mission within the North-east Coast of Ibiza-Tagomago Marine Reserve, on all transects, all sites combined (gregarious species excluded).

Figure 4. Average species richness per transect by site (rounded values are indicated in arabic numbers). The error bars (whiskers) correspond to the standard error, represented here only in positive value (+E.S.) for better display. The color indicates the area to which the site belongs.

Figure 5. Species richness per transect, averaged by area, all sites combined (rounded values are indicated in arabic numbers). Error bars correspond to standard error (+/- ES).

4.1.2 Average abundance

The mean total abundance of fish (gregarious species excluded) per transect, averaged per site, varied from 37.2 ind.125 m⁻² for site 19 and 40.8 ind.125 m⁻² in site 25 (North Outside MPA area) to 218.3 ind.125 m⁻² for site 14 and 144.8 ind.125 m⁻² for site 18 (North MPA area) (Fig. 6). The average abundance across all sites (gregarious species excluded) was 84.53 ind.125 m⁻². Sites 14 and 18 had a higher average abundance of *A. imberbis* (16.66 ind.125 m⁻²), *D. vulgaris* (17.66), *S. tinca* (15.33 ind.125 m⁻²), *S. viridensis* (50.0 ind.125 m⁻²) and *T. pavo* (52.33 ind.125 m⁻² respectively).

Figure 6. Mean total abundance of fish per transect averaged by site (values are indicated in arabic numbers). The whiskers correspond to the standard error (-/+ E.S.).

The Integral Reserve area did not significantly differ from any other area. The North Outside MPA area displayed a significantly lower abundance than in the North MPA or Tagomago Island areas, while it was not different from the one observed in the Integral Reserve, which was as well low (although not statistically significantly lower than the other areas, probably due to some intra-area variability) (Fig. 7, Kruskal-Wallis Pairwise comparisons, $p < 0.05$).

We also observed some species-specific differences between areas : *Apogon imberbis* is abundant in the North MPA area (Fig. 8). *Diplodus puntazzo* was observed in all areas but is more abundant in the Integral Reserve (1.41 ind.125 m⁻²).

Finally, numerous species were more abundant in the North MPA area than in the other areas, including *A. imberbis* (3.83 ind.125 m⁻²), *D. dentex* (0.45 ind.125 m⁻²), *S. viridensis* (9.04 ind.125 m⁻²).

Figure 7. Mean total abundance of fish by area (values are indicated in arabic numbers). The whiskers correspond to the standard error ($-/+$ E.S.). The color indicates the area. Letters illustrate the significance or non-significance of differences in mean given by statistical tests; two areas with no letters in common differ significantly from each other for the considered response variable.

Figure 8. Description of the assemblage of Teleosts observed (excluding gregarious species) in terms of mean abundance (ind/ 125 m⁻²) by observation area. The whiskers correspond to the standard error ($-E.S.$) for better display. The color indicates the area to which the species belongs.

4.1.3 Average Size (TL)

Overall, for each of the species of the Teleost assemblage identified, the individuals showed fairly similar average sizes (TL: Total Length) between the different areas (Fig. 9).

Within the Integral Reserve area, individuals were not larger than in the other areas studied. No real pattern could be extracted from the total length data.

Figure 9. Description of the assemblage of Teleosts observed (excluding gregarious species) in terms of average size of the individuals (TL: Total Length, in cm) by observation areas. The whiskers correspond to the standard error (-E.S.) for better display. The color indicates the area to which the species belongs.

4.1.4 Average Biomass

The mean total biomass per transect averaged per site (Fig. 10) varied from 544 g.125 m⁻² for site 19 (North Outside MPA) to 19 316 g.125 m⁻² for site 14 (North MPA area). The biomass average for all transects combined (gregarious species excluded) was 5000.24 g.125 m⁻². Sites located inside the North MPA area showed a higher average biomass than the other sites. Sites 12, 14 and 18 were characterized by a biomass superior to 10 000 g.125 m⁻² (respectively 11 944 g.125 m⁻², 19 316 g.125 m⁻² and 16 232 g.125 m⁻²). Site 14 was characterized by the largest biomass of *S. viridensis* recorded (9899.6 g.125 m⁻²). Site 18 (North MPA area) was characterized by a significant biomass of *S. salpa* (10 145 g.125 m⁻²). The Integral Reserve did not significantly differ from any other area.

Figure 10. Mean total biomass per transect (wet mass in g.125 m⁻²) averaged per site. The whiskers correspond to the standard error (+E.S.). Rounded values are indicated in arabic numbers. The color indicates the area to which the site belongs.

Regarding the biomass we've observed significant differences **between in and outside MPA areas**, particularly in the North. For instance, there was a significantly higher biomass in the North MPA area and as well in the Tagomago Island area compared to the North Outside MPA area (Fig. 11, Kruskal-Wallis Pairwise comparison, $p < 0.05$). Similarly, the South MPA area displayed a significantly higher biomass than the North Outside MPA area (Fig 11, Kruskal-Wallis Pairwise comparison, $p < 0.05$). However, there was no significant differences between the South MPA area and the South Outside MPA area. On average, biomass in the MPA was 4673 g.125m⁻² (Integral Reserve) and 6325 g.125m⁻² (partially protected zone) *versus* 2316 g.125m⁻² outside the MPA .

Figure 11. Mean total biomass per transect (wet mass in g.125 m⁻²) averaged per area. The whiskers correspond to the standard error (+/- E.S.). The color indicates the area to which the site belongs. Letters illustrate the significance or non-significance of differences in mean given by statistical tests; two areas with no letters in common differ significantly from each other for the considered response variable.

4.1.5 Emblematic Species

The emblematic species *E. marginatus* and *S. umbra* were mainly observed in the South MPA area and North MPA area (Fig. 12). Dusky groupers (*Epinephelus marginatus*) were observed in many sites. Tagomago Island area is where they were the most abundant (11 ind. in site 9). Mottled groupers (*Mycteroperca rubra*) were observed in two northern sites only: in site 12 (North MPA area), and site 21 (North Outside MPA area) where only one individual was observed at each site. Golden groupers (*Epinephelus costae*) were observed in site 10 (Integral Reserve area) and site 12 (North MPA area) respectively.

Concerning *Sciena umbra*, they were observed in four areas including the Integral Reserve where they were the most abundant (15 individuals) (Fig. 12).

Regarding total length, there were no significant differences between sites for any emblematic species (Fig. 13).

Figure 12. Total abundance per site of the emblematic species *E. marginatus*, *M. rubra* and *S. umbra*. Abundances are specified in arabic numbers (nb). The color indicates the area to which the site belongs.

Figure 13. Average size (TL in cm) per site of the emblematic species *E. marginatus*, *M. rubra* and *S. umbra* for sites where at least one of the species was present. The whiskers correspond to the standard error (- E.S.).

Biomass of the three emblematic species was slightly higher in the Integral Reserve area compared to other areas. *Epinephelus marginatus* biomass was higher in the Tagomago area than in other areas (Fig. 14).

Figure 14. Average biomass ($\text{g}/125 \text{ m}^2$) per site of the emblematic species *E. marginatus*, *M. rubra* and *S. umbra*. The whiskers correspond to the standard error ($- \text{S.E.}$). The color indicates the area to which the site belongs.

4.1.6 Species targeted by fishing

For some fished species (*D. annularis*, *D. sargus*, *D. dentex*, *M. surmuletus*, *S. scriba*, *S. salpa*, and *O. melanura*), the North MPA area seemed to stand out in terms of mean abundance (Fig. 15) and mean specific biomass (Fig. 16). *Dentex dentex* showed greater abundances and biomasses in the North MPA area (Fig. 15, Fig. 16) but not larger sizes (Fig. 17). *Serranus scriba* is the most ubiquitous species, and showed equivalent biomass, abundance and total length between areas (Fig. 15, Fig. 16, Fig. 17). The South MPA area stands out in terms of abundance for *D. sargus*, *M. surmuletus*, and *D. annularis*. The Integral Reserve area showed average abundances (Fig. 15) and average biomasses (Fig. 16) of *L. merula* and *D. puntazzo* more important than in the other areas, but individuals were no larger than in other areas. Concerning total length, overall there is no significant difference between areas for these species (Fig. 17). It was in the North MPA and South MPA areas that individuals of *D. sargus* and *D. annularis* were the most numerous (Fig. 15).

Figure 15. Description of the assemblage of Teleosts targeted by fishing observed in terms of abundance by transects (ind.125 m⁻²) averaged per area. The whiskers correspond to the standard error (- S.E.).

Figure 16. Description of the assemblage of Teleosts targeted by fishing observed in terms of mean biomass per transect (g.125 m⁻²) averaged per area. The whiskers correspond to the standard error (- S.E.).

Figure 17. Description of the assemblage of Teleosts targeted by fishing observed in terms of mean total length per transect ($g.125\ m^{-2}$) averaged per area. The whiskers correspond to the standard error ($-S.E.$).

4.2. Gradient analysis

Focusing on the $-\log$ of the ratio (abundance/biomass) allowed to detect a possible effect of protection: in fact, this $-\log$ ratio increases when the biomass increases at constant abundance, which is the case when individuals are larger.

In our data, we observed that in the southern part of the MPA, no clear pattern of the ratio appeared along the gradient going from the South Outside MPA area towards the Integral Reserve (Fig. 18). There even seemed to be a decrease as it got closer to the reserve on this side, suggesting there was no clear cut reserve effect inside the Integral Reserve for the species targeted by fishing; contrastingly, on the other side of the MPA, from the North-Outside area towards the center of the MPA and the Integral Reserve, an increase in this ratio tended to appear (Fig. 18). This log ratio seemed more important within the sites 12, 14 and 18 of the North MPA area, suggesting either a site effect (Fig. 19) or a tendency for the North-MPA area to be more favorable for fish populations in comparison to the outside unprotected area.

Figure 18. Gradient analysis: values (dots) of the $-\log(\text{Abundance}/\text{Biomass})$ for fished species by site, and regression lines. The regression lines describe the South-Center gradient and North-Center gradient. Sites 10 and 11 are located inside the Integral Reserve area. Each dot represents a transect. N.B.: this $-\log$ ratio increases when the biomass increases at constant abundance, which is the case when the individuals are larger.

Figure 19. Gradient analysis. $-\log$ ratio (abundance/biomass) of species targeted by fishing (overall per site). N.B.: this $-\log$ ratio increases when the biomass increases at constant abundance, which is the case when the individuals are larger.

4.3. Comparison with Other Mediterranean MPAs

Differences in average biomass and average abundance between the different MPAs may be due to natural differences such as environmental factors in specific localities influencing larval input or fish growth. Comparison of ratios of respectively mean abundance or mean biomass from interior *versus* exterior of a given MPA therefore allowed us to overcome the influence of these local conditions: data from other MPAs studied as part of the Odyssey of AMPs program and from previous studies (BIOMEX program, Harmelin-Vivien et al., 2008), made it possible to put our results in perspective (Tab. 1, Fig. 20-21).

As regards abundances: the Tagomago MPA Integral Reserve (no-take zone) had both the lowest average abundance and lowest abundance ratio in *vs out* compared to other no-take areas previously studied in other MPAs (BIOMEX and Odyssey of AMPs) (Fig. 20-21). On the other hand, for the partially protected part of the Tagomago MPA, the ratio of mean abundance inside *versus* outside was on average greater than the average abundance ratio recorded in mediterranean MPAs (such as Bonifacio partially protected zone, Bonifacio no-take zone, or Dilek Peninsula).

As regards biomass: for both the Integral Reserve and the partially protected part, mean biomass remained lower than the biomasses observed in the fully protected areas (no-take zones) of MPAs studied as part of the BIOMEX project (Fig. 21). Besides, the biomass ratio inside *versus* outside the protected zone recorded for the Tagomago MPA (partial protection) was greater than the one for the integral reserve, and it was greater than the mean biomass ratio recorded in Mediterranean MPAs (Fig. 20).

In summary, our data, as already suggested in part 4.2, indicated that the partially protected zone of Tagomago MPA does produce a significant positive effect on fish production, as observed in partially protected zones in other mediterranean MPAs (e.g.: Bonifacio ZPR), while the Integral Reserve proves no efficiency.

Figure 20. Evaluation of the effectiveness of the protection put in place in each MPA (dots) studied in the BIOMEX and Odyssey of MPAs projects, expressed as the ratios inside the zones with protection status (ZNP and RI = No-Take Zones; ZPR = Partially protected zones) *versus* outside the zones with protection status of each MPA, for abundance (x-axis) and biomass (y-axis) respectively. Dotted lines indicate the average ratios (biomass and abundance respectively) found for a set of representative Mediterranean MPAs (i.e. with no-take zones actually implemented and respected) by the study of Giakoumi and his collaborators (Giakoumi et al., 2017).

Figure 21. Descriptors (average biomass and total abundance) of teleost communities in the protected and unprotected areas of the different MPAs studied in the Mediterranean - 2023 data from Tagomago MPA are presented alongside those of western study areas of the BIOMEX program (Harmelin-Vivien et al., 2008) and the MPA Odyssey project (2021–2023). Increasing gradation of protection: Unprotected < Partially protected < No-Take Zone (protected).

Table 1 : Mean species richness, mean abundance and mean biomass recorded in different Mediterranean MPAs during the BIOMEX (Harmelin-Vivien et al., 2008) and MPA Odyssey (2021–2023) projects. Increasing gradation of protection: Unprotected < Partially protected < No-Take Zone (protected). NB: within the Dilek Peninsula MPA, "Partially protected" status prohibits professional fishing and authorizes recreational fishing, within the Tagomago MPA, "Partially protected" status prohibits spearfishing and imposes limited license for professional fishing. In all other MPAs, "Partially protected" status prohibits recreational fishing and authorizes professional fishing. In Lastovo Islands Nature Parks, the No-Take Zones are not yet effective and are only at the project stage.

Marine Protected Area	Project	Protection type	Mean species richness	Mean abundance (ind.125 m ⁻²)	Mean Biomass (g.125 m ⁻²)
RN Cerbère-Banyuls	BIOMEX	No-Take Zone	11.2	79.2	16 300.0
RN Cerbère-Banyuls	BIOMEX	Unprotected	10.8	70.5	4 000.0
Cabo de Palos	BIOMEX	No-Take Zone	12.9	99.0	28 200.0
Cabo de Palos	BIOMEX	Unprotected	9.8	60.1	2 900.0
Cabrera	BIOMEX	No-Take Zone	14.1	93.0	13 600.0
Cabrera	BIOMEX	Unprotected	13.9	71.6	2 700.0
Carry le Rouet	BIOMEX	No-Take Zone	13.1	99.3	16 300.0

Carry le Rouet	BIOMEX	Unprotected	12.4	64.1	2 400.0
Medes	BIOMEX	No-Take Zone	13.8	61.1	17 500.0
Medes	BIOMEX	Unprotected	10.2	31.5	2 700.0
Tabarca	BIOMEX	No-Take Zone	12.3	113.6	9 400.0
Tabarca	BIOMEX	Unprotected	13.3	98.3	5 300.0
PNMCCA	MPA Odyssey	No-Take Zone	10.4	58.0	2 771.0
PNMCCA	MPA Odyssey	Unprotected	9.7	56.7	1 908.0
Dilek Peninsula	MPA Odyssey	Partially protected	9.7	106.7	3 909.0
Dilek Peninsula	MPA Odyssey	Unprotected	10.2	100.0	3 720.0
RN Bouches de Bonifacio	MPA Odyssey	No-Take Zone	11.7	106.2	7 185.0
RN Bouches de Bonifacio	MPA Odyssey	Partially protected	12.3	118.2	6 654.0
RN Bouches de Bonifacio	MPA Odyssey	Unprotected	10.9	85.6	1 829.0
PNRC / RN Scandola	MPA Odyssey	Integral Reserve / No-Take Zone	12.3	152.8	14 209.0
PNRC / RN Scandola	MPA Odyssey	Cantonment / No- Take Zone	11.6	90	30 861.0
PNRC / RN Scandola	MPA Odyssey	Partially protected	11.4	121.0	6 694.0
PNRC / RN Scandola	MPA Odyssey	Unprotected	10.3	76.5	2 398.0
Tagomago MPA (Ibiza)	MPA Odyssey	Integral Reserve / No-Take Zone	10.1	32.8	4 673.0
Tagomago MPA (Ibiza)	MPA Odyssey	Partially protected	11.6	100	6 325.0
Tagomago MPA (Ibiza)	MPA Odyssey	Unprotected	9.3	70	2 316.0
Lastovo Islands Nature Park	MPA Odyssey	Future No-Take Zones (but still unprotected)	11.2	74.3	2 646.0
Lastovo Islands Nature Park	MPA Odyssey	Unprotected	11.7	77.5	2 296.0

5. Discussion

5.1. Methodology Robustness

The Underwater Visual Census (UVC) method is a well-tested approach that gives reliable results if the operators are previously trained and inter-calibrated, a precaution which was taken here (Harmelin-Vivien et al., 1985). Different and more recent methodological methods exist, for example with a transect width of variable dimensions depending on the species considered (Prato et al., 2017), nevertheless the classic version of UVC was favoured here to compare the results with existing literature on prior studies (Harmelin-Vivien et al., 2008).

Besides, it is worth remembering here that this method is suitable for the inventory of necto-benthic vagile fauna only. It is therefore not surprising that our data do not contain many observations of crypto-benthic species, such as Scorpaenidae.

One of the difficulties we faced was to carry out sampling at constant habitat: targeted habitat (sublittoral rocky reefs between 7 to 15 meters deep) was not always present, sometimes leading us to consider a mixed rocky habitat which may present a partial covering by *P. oceanica* meadows (taking care not to exceed 50% cover). This variability in habitat characteristics between our samples inevitably induces a relative bias which must be taken into account when interpreting the results.

It should also be noted that, following spatial configuration constraints, the number of study sites by area has not been constant (e.g. in the Integral Reserve), which must lead us to moderate some interpretations.

5.2. Overall State of Fish Assemblages

Overall, the inventories of teleost fish assemblages we carried out report the presence of typical fish assemblages of the NW Mediterranean infralittoral rocky reefs. Some areas presented populations with relatively low specific richness and abundance, dominated by small size classes in comparison with other areas of the NW Mediterranean (Estaque et al., 2023; Garcia-Rubies and Zabala, 1990; Richaume et al., 2023). Observed values are comparable to those registered by Coll et al. (2020) for different protected localities in the Balearic Islands, like some sites in Cabrera (Illots, Conillera, Rates o Estells). Globally, the Tagomago MPA seemed to already show some protection efficiency as the biomass and abundances in *vs out* ratios were higher than the average observed in the Mediterranean (Fig. 20).

5.3. Effects of Protected Zones (No-Take and Partially Protected Zones)

5.3.1. Integral Reserve of the North-east Coast of Ibiza-Tagomago Marine Reserve

The Integral Reserve (no-take zone) within the Tagomago MPA appeared to be exhibiting limited effects on protecting fish populations. Our results indicated that total fish lengths

within the Integral Reserve were comparable to other areas, suggesting that protective measures may not be significantly influencing fish size. Abundance levels, notably higher in the northern zone studied, seemed more influenced by geomorphological features than the protection status of the Integral Reserve. Given that this MPA is relatively recent (established in 2018), the absence of direct impacts on fish size and numbers at this early stage might be considered normal as reserve effects usually appear after a few years of protection (Halpern et al., 2006; Williams et al., 2016) (Rojo et al., 2021). Furthermore, our results are consistent with the 2021 study report (Garcia-Charton et al., 2021) which showed the limited impact of protective measures within the Integral Reserve, with no discernible patterns across various marine reserves and few interannual variations detected.

The size of the Integral Reserve, currently less than 360ha (268ha), raises questions about its effectiveness, with a suggestion to expand its area to enhance its impact and benefits. Indeed, Di Franco and collaborators (2018) underlined the minimum size of fully protected area should be 360 ha for observing reserve effects on fish populations such as an increase of the density of local populations of coastal marine species (*e.g. Diplodus* spp. *Serranus* spp. *Epinephelus* spp., *S. salpa*). The Integral Reserve demonstrated its efficiency in terms of diversity, as 3 out of four emblematic species were observed within its boundaries, such as the emblematic golden grouper *Epinephelus costae*, underscoring the ecological importance of this area within the broader marine reserve context. On the other hand, it is worth noting that geomorphological features may have caused the observed low levels of fish descriptors, since the bottom of the Integral reserve is mainly covered by sandy habitat and seagrass meadows, with rare blocks and rocky outcrops (such as site 10).

Surveillance measures, particularly in proximity to Es Figueral and Cala Llenya, where a probable higher level of pressure from visitors and fishers exists compared to the isolated northern areas, are crucial for the success of conservation efforts (Claudet et al., 2020; Giakoumi et al., 2017; Sala and Giakoumi, 2018). We then propose (section 6) yearly visual fish countings to monitor the evolution of reserve effectiveness over time.

Previous authors showed the Tagomago MPA partially protected zone revealed intermediate levels of abundance and biomass compared to the Integral Reserve and non-protected areas (Garcia-Charton et al., 2021). This reinforces the significance of maintaining buffer zones around integral reserves, even though their overall effectiveness might be somewhat lower. These buffer areas might serve as insurance against excessive pressures outside the reserve, especially if accompanied by adequate regulation and surveillance. Additionally, they play an important role in preventing the "edge effect" phenomenon, where spillover to adjacent unprotected areas creates a gradient of abundance and/or biomass from inside to outside the marine reserve (Hackradt et al., 2014; Harmelin-Vivien et al., 2008). This offset is crucial, as excessive pressure at the very limits of the protected area could lead to a decrease in density within the reserve itself (Ohayon et al., 2021).

For all these reasons, as perspectives, enlarging and moving the Integral reserve towards another location, with a more diversified complex substratum, and surrounding the NTZ with partially protected zones is identified as a good alternative: this is discussed in the next section (see section 6 – Management Recommendations).

5.3.2. Areas outside the Integral Reserve: the partially protected zone of the Tagomago MPA

The partially protected zone of the Tagomago MPA showed fish assemblages in an overall good state. Fish abundances under this intermediate level of protection was particularly important in the northern parts (North MPA area). Indeed, in the North MPA area (sites 12 to 18) large fish schools observations such as *Sphyraena viridensis*, *Sarpa salpa* or *Diplodus* spp. (including *D. vulgaris* and *D. sargus*) were made. It thus might be interesting to strengthen the protection level in the North MPA zone, for example by creating a no-take zone within this perimeter. The South MPA area (sites 1 to 6) also displayed results comparable to the Integral Reserve area in terms of fish abundance. In this area, the mean abundance per 125 m² of *L. merula*, *D. annularis* and *L. viridis* were higher or similar to the results observed inside the Integral Reserve. *Sciaena umbra* and *Epinephelus marginatus*, two emblematic species, were also encountered within this area and more frequently observed compared to other areas.

Within the partially protected zone of Tagomago MPA, and particularly in the Tagomago Island area, the seabed displayed a favorable habitat characterized by rocks and shallow rocky reefs. The relatively good state of fish populations that we observed in this area (Fig. 14, Fig. 15) prompts inquiry into the factors contributing to such conditions. The reasonable results observed may be attributed to a combination of the private status of the island, its isolated location, substratum, and potentially lower pressure from tourism.

All those assets identified within the partially protected zone of the MPA led us to the proposed management perspectives exposed in section 6, aiming at taking advantage of the high potential of such sites.

5.3.3. Comparison with Other MPAs and Proposition of an Alternative Scenario for the Tagomago MPA

Data from previous studies such as the BIOMEX program (Harmelin-Vivien et al., 2008) and the Odyssey of AMPs project (2021-2023), allowed us to put our results into perspective (Tab. 1).

The partially protected zone on the northeast coast of the Tagomago MPA seemed to stand out among studied zones, offering a suitable habitat for fish populations, a relatively isolated location and protection measures leading to greater fish abundance. The discernible trends in Tagomago MPA suggested that observed fish assemblages lean more towards geomorphological influences than explicit reserve impacts given the Integral Reserve recency and size. A comparative analysis with other MPAs studied within the framework of MPA Odyssey project (Corsican MPAs and the Dilek Peninsula MPA), brings a nuanced understanding of fish occurrence and dominance: fish

community structures revealed that dominant species in Tagomago MPA may vary from those found in other Mediterranean MPAs, underscoring the interplay of environmental factors and protective measures. In the Tagomago MPA assemblages were dominated by a diverse cortege of species characteristic of shallow rocky reefs : *T. pavo*, *D. vulgaris*, *S. salpa*, *C. julis*, *S. tinca*. In comparison, in Dilek the assemblages were dominated by fewer dominant species such as *D. vulgaris*, *C. julis* and *O. melanura*, while in Scandola assemblages were dominated mostly by *S. tinca*, followed by *O. melanura* and *C. julis*.

The fish biomass in Tagomago MPA is equivalent to mediterranean MPAs such as in Bonifacio marine reserve (RNBB) and is superior to PNMCC (Cap Corse). However, biomass is inferior to some historic MPAs such as RNS (Scandola). Tagomago MPA had higher abundance and biomass ratios than the averages of Mediterranean MPAs which shows its efficiency. Indeed, the abundance ratio in Tagomago is superior to Scandola cantonnement, Dilek Peninsula, Lastovo, Banyuls, and Bonifacio (ZNP and ZPR). However biomass ratio is way below some integral reserves such as Scandola integral reserve and Bonifacio ZNP. This underlines the need for more conservation efforts.

In summary, the Tagomago MPA displayed already some good results as regards its fish communities, with indicators highlighting the high potential of its marine habitats and some first encouraging outcomes of protection measures, notably in the partially protected zone. On this basis, we propose in the following section a complementary alternative scenario for the management measures' design.

6. Management Recommendations

6.1. Future Protections to be Implemented: Effective Implementation of NTZ, Professional Fishing Reserved Areas Surrounding the NTZ and Recreational Fishing Regulations

6.1.1. General Approach

Given the recency of the Tagomago MPA and the observed limited influence of protective measures so far, managers might consider adapting and strengthening measures over time. Since reserve effect is often observed after a few years of protection (Halpern et al., 2006; Rojo et al., 2021; Williams et al., 2016), it might be interesting to regularly review and update regulations to address emerging conservation challenges and promote sustainable fisheries management in partnership with local stakeholders (Espinoza-Tenorio et al., 2015; McDonald et al., 2020; Thompson, 2008).

Authorities of the Tagomago MPA **are currently considering an enlargement of the MPA perimeter** (see current management plan map in Fig. 1). Our following recommendations are given as suggestions to be implemented in the framework of such revision of the MPA management plan. Indeed, as highlighted by our data, fish communities, and therefore fishermen, do not actually fully benefit from this MPA status in Tagomago MPA. The reason for these mitigated results is the absence of really effective and adequate No Take Zones (NTZ) within the boundaries of the MPA. Such zones should not be taken as "closed" or as "lost fishing ground", on the contrary, many scientific papers (Harmelin-

Vivien et al., 2008) have demonstrated that they produce extra biomass that is exported and become available for fisheries outside. In Carry Le Rouet (France), it has been demonstrated that one 85 ha NTZ produced 106 tonnes of fish biomass each year.

In Tagomago MPA, such a NTZ should enhance the available biomass. By surrounding NTZ with zones where only professional fishing is allowed (Professional Fishing Reserved Areas- PFRA) would ensure that the extra biomass produced is directly benefiting the professional fishermen community. For two examples in Corsica (Natural Reserve of Scandola and Bonifacio) in such areas where fishing is only allowed to professional, the biomass present is 4 and 5 times higher than in open areas with no restriction. In Bonifacio, the catch per unit effort (CPUE) has increased by 60% to 80% (80% for species targeted by spearfishing) for fishermen six years after banning recreational fishing from such areas.

Our data suggested that such buffer areas could serve as a crucial intermediary between fully protected areas and unprotected zones, such as we observed in the North MPA area with high abundance and biomass for several species (e.g *S. viridensis*). These buffer areas act as a safeguard against excessive pressures outside the integral reserve, contributing to the overall effectiveness of the conservation strategy (Claudet et al., 2008; Di Lorenzo et al., 2016). Consequently, such modules coupling NTZ surrounded by areas reserved for professional fishing (PFRA) are **the core of our recommendations for the MPA**. They are the key to combine biodiversity protection, restoration of the halieutic resources, and economical wealth for local fishermen.

Our study allowed us to identify some sites richer than average with teleost assemblages in a better state of conservation than the other sites studied and with remarkable habitats. These sites are examples of good candidates for prioritizing the effective implementation of a renovated NTZ plan. The scientific community has shown that strong protection zones with a surface area of at least 3.6 km² are preferable (Di Franco et al., 2018). Even though it is not everywhere easy or possible to create such big NTZs in the context of the Tagomago MPA, it is essential to consider this and increase the surface area of the existing NTZ with a view to optimizing the benefits offered by strong protection. The next section presents such scenarios.

6.1.2. Transferring and Enlarging the Integral Reserve (NTZ)

Our results highlighted a lack of efficiency from the Integral Reserve, probably due to its small size, location and age. We recommend it would be interesting to expand, relocate and reinforce the existing No-Take Zone within the Tagomago MPA. Considering the small size of the current Integral Reserve, and its topographical features, it may probably be interesting to switch this no-take zone for another, or even two different NTZs. This can further safeguard critical habitats and vulnerable species, and will favour spillover effects in the future.

In view of the above-mentioned results and discussions concerning the attractiveness of the Tagomago North zone in terms of geomorphological features, fish diversity and

abundance, the proposed scenario includes two potential No-Take Zones (North East NTZ and Tagomago Island NTZ), one of which is larger than 3.6 km², surrounded by Professional Fishing Reserved Areas (PFRAs) (Fig. 22). Indeed, NTZs should be surrounded by such partially protected buffer zones: additionally to their benefits previously explained, such zones reserved for professional fishermen as well allow them to be considered in the decision-making, encourage them to take part into the management and to increase the conservation effort by supporting the NTZs.

6.1.3 Stakeholders Involvement : Increasing the Area of Zones Reserved for Small-Scale Professional Fishing

A strategic approach to improve the sustainability of small-scale professional fishing within Tagomago MPA involves exploring successful models, such as those observed in regions like the Bonifacio MPA in Corsica. Our previous work has shown (particularly in the Scandola Nature Reserve - Corsica; Estaque et al, 2023) that partially protected zones reserved for professional fishing (PFRAs) provide good benefits, sometimes comparable to those provided by a No Take-Zone. Within the Tagomago MPA, this type of Professional Fishing Reserved Areas should be considered as a complement to NTZs (Fig. 22).

Inspired by these positive outcomes, where protective measures have proven effectiveness, there is an opportunity to consider the implementation of a similar framework in the North-east Coast of Ibiza-Tagomago Marine Reserve. By expanding the areas exclusively reserved for small-scale professional fishing, the aim is not only to sustain local fisheries but also to target conservation objectives observed in other Mediterranean regions. These zones could serve as dedicated spaces for small scale fishing practices, contributing to the economic well-being of local communities while minimizing the impact on the broader marine biodiversity. We summarized (Fig. 22) what could be a desirable new spatial planning using this approach, but the thoughtful delineation of these zones could be realized through a co-management approach, with concertation of the local fishing community. It would be a way of drawing upon lessons learned from successful initiatives, such as in the Parc Marin de la Côte Bleue MPA (France).

Figure 22 - Map showing the implementation scenario of two sectors both including No-Take Zones (NTZ, blue green polygons) surrounded by Professional Fishing Reserved Area (PFRA, brown polygons), placed according to the conclusions of this study which highlights the potential of the north-east coast of Ibiza and the island of Tagomago.

Based on our scenario calculations (Tab. 2), the implementation of No-Take Zones surrounded by zones reserved for professional fishermen (Professional Fishing Reserved Area, PFRA) would allow fish production to increase significantly compared to the present state: from 287 345 kg.year⁻¹ to 516 490 kg.year⁻¹ (i.e. 185% higher) for the North East sector (encompassing NTZ+PFRA) and from 175 114 kg.year⁻¹ to 323 835 kg.year⁻¹ (i.e. 180% higher) for the Tagomago Island sector (encompassing NTZ+PFRA). This increase will be directly available through “spill-over” effect in zones specially reserved for small scale professional fishing (PFRA, Fig. 22).

Table 2 : Sectors (as referred to in Fig. 22) and Total production in kg per year. Current production, different scenario's productions and production increase (%) are presented for each different sectors. The first scenario corresponds to the **potential production** increased by the exedentary production resulting from setting up the **NTZ** (i.e exedentary production available around the NTZ once protected *versus* production available when not protected), while the rest of the sector remains open to all types of fishing. The second scenario corresponds to the **potential production** increased by two exedentary productions resulting (a) from the setting up of the **NTZ** and (b) resulting from the setting up of the surrounding **PFRA**.

Sectors	Surface NTZ/PFRA	Current Production (kg.year ⁻¹)	Scenario 1 - Potential Production NTZ (t.year ⁻¹)	Scenario 2 - Potential Production NTZ + PFRA (t.year ⁻¹)	Global production increase
Tagomago Island	17,3%	175 114	174 584	323 835	185 %
North East	30,0%	287 345	286 176	516 490	180 %

6.1.4 Maintaining and Enforcing Surveillance, Regulation of Recreational Fishing, and Public Awareness

Once recommended management measures (see previous section) are set up, adequate **enforcement** is crucial to prevent illegal activities and maintain the integrity of a marine reserve. Only “serious” surveillance allows a MPA efficiency (Claudet et al., 2020; Rojo et al., 2019; Zupan et al., 2018). Apart from surveillance, it includes monitoring fishing practices both within and outside the MPA boundaries. Implementing measures to prevent the “edge effect” from offsetting conservation gains within a NTZ itself is also important (Ohayon et al., 2021). This may involve strategic management of fishing pressures at the boundaries of the NTZs.

The effective management and surveillance of **recreational fishing** within the Tagomago MPA is necessary, especially considering the region's popularity among tourists with almost 2 million tourists in Ibiza in 2018 (Pérez et al., 2020). Implementing and rigorously enforcing regulations for recreational fishing is vital to strike a balance between the enjoyment of visitors and the conservation of marine biodiversity (Arlinghaus and Cooke, 2009; Granek et al., 2008; Lewin et al., 2006). Such regulations encompass stringent measures such as catch limits already existing, carefully chosen gear types, and the demarcation of specific fishing areas within the reserve. Catch limits, such as the existing ones, help mitigate the risk of over-exploitation, ensuring the sustainability of fish populations and maintaining ecological balance (Van Poorten et al., 2013). The careful selection of gear types, with an emphasis on environmentally friendly and non-intrusive methods, further minimizes the impact on marine habitats. Regular awareness campaigns and educational initiatives targeting both locals and tourists can contribute to fostering a culture of responsible angling within the Tagomago MPA.

Finally, it might be interesting to implement educational programs to raise awareness about the importance of marine conservation within the local community, among fishermen and other stakeholders such as tourists (Thompson, 2008; Urquhart et al., 2014).

6.2. Including Various Essential Habitats in The Protection Scheme

Furthermore, it seems imperative to delve into strategies for the protection of vital habitats such as fish nurseries to pursue effective conservation (Cheminée, 2012). Further local research should be done on the identification and preservation of these essential habitats that serve for numerous Mediterranean fish species, an indispensable role in the early life stages and reproductive cycles (Cheminée et al., 2021). Management measures should therefore include nursery habitats to prevent their loss or transformation, which would compromise their function (Cheminée et al., 2017). In coastal zones, various habitats in the infralittoral mosaic and their interfaces play this role and should benefit from strong protective measures (Cheminée et al., 2021).

More particularly, three habitats in the depth range of 0-15 meters are notably concerned: marine forests covering infralittoral rocks (Sargassaceae, Fucales, Phaeophyceae, such as forests of the genus *Cystoseira sensu lato*), heterogeneous shallow bottoms (blocks and gravel on very shallow gentle slopes), and *Posidonia oceanica* meadows. To preserve these habitats, protective measures should not directly target fishing but rather other human activities:

- For seagrass meadows, impacts from ship anchoring can be limited through mooring management.
- For heterogeneous rocky shallow bottoms : located at the bottom of bays and coves, this habitat is vulnerable to coastline changes, urbanization, etc. To avoid future destruction of these essential habitats and the juvenile fish assemblages associated, localizing these nursery grounds represents a major challenge for their preservation.

By implementing targeted conservation efforts for these specific habitats, we would not only aim to contribute to the preservation of biodiversity but also fortify the resilience of the entire ecosystem. Collaborative initiatives with scientific communities and local stakeholders are essential to formulate and implement effective protection measures, fostering a comprehensive approach to marine habitat conservation (Cheminée et al., 2020). Regular monitoring and adaptive management will be key components in ensuring the success and adaptability of these strategies over time.

6.3. Future Monitoring

To enforce conservation within the North-east Coast of Ibiza-Tagomago MPA, it is advisable to establish a comprehensive and continuous monitoring program to track the effectiveness of the implemented conservation measures and the overall health of the marine reserve. This involves regular population assessments such as the 2021 study

(García-Charton et al., 2021), habitat surveys, and the incorporation of advanced research techniques to detect changes over time.

By addressing these future protections, the North-east Coast of Ibiza-Tagomago MPA can further enhance its conservation efforts, contributing to the long-term sustainability of marine ecosystems and the preservation of biodiversity. Collaboration with local communities, scientists, and relevant authorities is essential for the successful implementation of these measures. Regular reviews and adaptive management strategies should be employed to ensure the ongoing success of conservation initiatives within the MPA.

7. Bibliography

- Arlinghaus, R., Cooke, S., 2009. Recreational Fisheries: Socioeconomic Importance, Conservation Issues and Management Challenges. pp. 39–58. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781444303179.ch3>
- Arpa Vila, M., García Charton, J.A., Cuadros, A., Orenes, V., Pozo, M., 2020. Informe Tècnic per a la Direcció General de Pesca i Medi Marí del Govern de les Illes Balears (Rapport technique). Govern de les Illes Balears, Illes des Baléares.
- Cheminée, A., 2012. Ecological functions, transformations and management of infralittoral rocky habitats from the North-western Mediterranean: the case of fish (Teleostei) nursery habitats (PhD thesis). University of Nice, Nice.
- Cheminée, A., Direach, L.L., Rouanet, E., Astruch, P., Goujard, A., Blanfuné, A., Bonhomme, D., Chassaing, L., Jouvenel, J.-Y., Ruitton, S., Thibaut, T., Harmelin-Vivien, M., 2020. Typology of fish nurseries in shallow Mediterranean coastal zones: all habitats matter (preprint). In Review. <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-118728/v1>
- Cheminée, A., Le Direach, L., Rouanet, E., Astruch, P., Goujard, A., Blanfuné, A., Bonhomme, D., Chassaing, L., Jouvenel, J.-Y., Ruitton, S., Thibaut, T., Harmelin-Vivien, M., 2021. All shallow coastal habitats matter as nurseries for Mediterranean juvenile fish. *Sci Rep* 11, 14631. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-021-93557-2>
- Cheminée, A., Rider, M., Lenfant, P., Zawadzki, A., Mercière, A., Crec'hriou, R., Mercader, M., Saragoni, G., Neveu, R., Ternon, Q., Pastor, J., 2017. Shallow rocky nursery habitat for fish: Spatial variability of juvenile fishes among this poorly protected essential habitat. *Marine Pollution Bulletin* 119, 245–254. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2017.03.051>
- Claudet, J., Loiseau, C., Sostres, M., Zupan, M., 2020. Underprotected Marine Protected Areas in a Global Biodiversity Hotspot. *One Earth* 2, 380–384. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.oneear.2020.03.008>
- Claudet, J., Osenberg, C.W., Benedetti-Cecchi, L., Domenici, P., García-Charton, J.-A., Pérez-Ruzafa, A., Badalamenti, F., Bayle-Sempere, J., Brito, A., Bulleri, F., Culioli, J.-M., Dimech, M., Falcón, J.M., Guala, I., Milazzo, M., Sánchez-Meca, J., Somerfield, P.J., Stobart, B., Vandeperre, F., Valle, C., Planes, S., 2008. Marine reserves: size and age do matter. *Ecol Lett* 11, 481–489. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1461-0248.2008.01166.x>
- Coll Montserrat, J., Reñones, O., Moranta Mesquida, J., Alvarez Berastegui, D., Cardona

- Pascual, L., 2020. Els peixos dels fons durs infralitorals de l'arxipèlag de Cabrera: efectes dels 25 anys de parc nacional, in: Arxipèlag de Cabrera: història natural, 2020, ISBN 978-84-09-23487-5, pàgs. 243-276. Presented at the Arxipèlag de Cabrera: història natural, Societat d'Història Natural de les Balears, pp. 243-276.
- Di Franco, A., Plass-Johnson, J.G., Di Lorenzo, M., Meola, B., Claudet, J., Gaines, S.D., García-Charton, J.A., Giakoumi, S., Grorud-Colvert, K., Hackradt, C.W., Micheli, F., Guidetti, P., 2018. Linking home ranges to protected area size: The case study of the Mediterranean Sea. *Biological Conservation* 221, 175-181. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2018.03.012>
- Di Lorenzo, M., Claudet, J., Guidetti, P., 2016. Spillover from marine protected areas to adjacent fisheries has an ecological and a fishery component. *Journal for Nature Conservation* 32, 62-66. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jnc.2016.04.004>
- Espinoza-Tenorio, A., Espejel, I., Wolff, M., 2015. From adoption to implementation? An academic perspective on Sustainable Fisheries Management in a developing country. *Marine Policy* 62, 252-260.
- Estaque, T., Richaume, J., Cheminee, A., Bianchimani, O., Ody, A., Personnic, S., Ody, D., 2023. Odyssée des Aires Marines Protégées - Parc naturel Régional de Corse et Réserve Naturelle de Scandola. (No. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10663851>).
- García-Rubies, A., Zabala, M., 1990. Effects of total fishing prohibition on the rocky fish assemblages of Medes Islands marine reserve (NW Mediterranean). *Scientia Marina (Barcelona)* 54, 317-328.
- Giakoumi, S., Scianna, C., Plass-Johnson, J., Micheli, F., Grorud-Colvert, K., Thiriet, P., Claudet, J., Di Carlo, G., Di Franco, A., Gaines, S.D., García-Charton, J.A., Lubchenco, J., Reimer, J., Sala, E., Guidetti, P., 2017. Ecological effects of full and partial protection in the crowded Mediterranean Sea: a regional meta-analysis. *Sci Rep* 7, 8940. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-017-08850-w>
- Granek, E.F., Madin, E.M.P., Brown, M.A., Figueira, W., Cameron, D.S., Hogan, Z., Kristianson, G., de Villiers, P., Williams, J.E., Post, J., Zahn, S., Arlinghaus, R., 2008. Engaging Recreational Fishers in Management and Conservation: Global Case Studies. *Conservation Biology* 22, 1125-1134.
- Hackradt, C.W., García-Charton, J.A., Harmelin-Vivien, M., Pérez-Ruzafa, Á., Le Diréach, L., Bayle-Sempere, J., Charbonnel, E., Ody, D., Reñones, O., Sanchez-Jerez, P., 2014. Response of Rocky Reef Top Predators (Serranidae: Epinephelinae) in and Around Marine Protected Areas in the Western Mediterranean Sea. *PLoS ONE* 9, e98206.
- Halpern, B.S., Regan, H.M., Possingham, H.P., McCarthy, M.A., 2006. Accounting for uncertainty in marine reserve design. *Ecology Letters* 9, 2-11. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1461-0248.2005.00827.x>
- Harmelin, J.G., 1987. Structure et variabilité de l'ichtyofaune d'une zone rocheuse protégée en Méditerranée (Parc national de Port-Cros, France). *P.S.Z.N. 1: Marine Ecology* 8, 263-284.
- Harmelin-Vivien, M., Le Diréach, L., Bayle-Sempere, J., Charbonnel, E., García-Charton, J.A., Ody, D., Pérez-Ruzafa, A., Reñones, O., Sánchez-Jerez, P., Valle, C., 2008. Gradients of abundance and biomass across reserve boundaries in six Mediterranean marine protected areas: Evidence of fish spillover? *Biological Conservation* 141, 1829-1839. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2008.04.029>
- Harmelin-Vivien, M.L., Harmelin, J.G., Chauvet, C., Duval, C., Galzin, R., Lejeune, P., Barnabé, G., Blanc, F., Chevalier, R., Duclerc, J., Lasserre, G., 1985. Évaluation visuelle des peuplements et populations de Poissons : méthodes et problèmes. *Rev. Ecol. (Terre vie)* 40, 467-539.
- Lewin, W.-C., Arlinghaus, R., Mehner, T., 2006. Documented and Potential Biological Impacts of Recreational Fishing: Insights for Management and Conservation.

- Reviews in Fisheries Science 14, 305–367.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/10641260600886455>
- McDonald, G., Wilson, M., Veríssimo, D., Twohey, R., Clemence, M., Apistar, D., Box, S., Butler, P., Cadiz, F.C., Campbell, S.J., Cox, C., Effron, M., Gaines, S., Jakub, R., Mancao, R.H., Rojas, P.T., Tirona, R.S., Vianna, G., 2020. Catalyzing sustainable fisheries management through behavior change interventions. *Conserv Biol* 34, 1176–1189. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cobi.13475>
- Ohayon, S., Granot, I., Belmaker, J., 2021. A meta-analysis reveals edge effects within marine protected areas. *Nat Ecol Evol* 5, 1301–1308.
<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41559-021-01502-3>
- Pérez, D.M.G., Martín, J.M.M., Martínez, J.M.G., Sáez-Fernández, F.J., 2020. An Analysis of the Cost of Water Supply Linked to the Tourism Industry. An Application to the Case of the Island of Ibiza in Spain. *Water* 12, 2006.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/w12072006>
- Prato, G., Thiriet, P., Franco, A.D., Francour, P., 2017. Enhancing fish Underwater Visual Census to move forward assessment of fish assemblages: An application in three Mediterranean Marine Protected Areas. *PLOS ONE* 12, e0178511.
<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0178511>
- Richaume, J., Estaque, T., Ody, D., Bianchimani, O., Ody, A., Personnic, S., Cheminee, A., 2023. Odyssée des Aires Marines Protégées Rapport de la mission 2022 au sein de la Réserve Naturelle des Bouches de Bonifacio (Rapport technique). Septentrion Environnement, Marseille.
- Rojo, I., Anadón, J.D., García-Charton, J.A., 2021. Exceptionally high but still growing predatory reef fish biomass after 23 years of protection in a Marine Protected Area. *PLOS ONE* 16, e0246335. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0246335>
- Rojo, I., Sánchez-Meca, J., García-Charton, J.A., 2019. Small-sized and well-enforced Marine Protected Areas provide ecological benefits for piscivorous fish populations worldwide. *Marine Environmental Research* 149, 100–110.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marenvres.2019.06.005>
- Sala, E., Giakoumi, S., 2018. No-take marine reserves are the most effective protected areas in the ocean. *ICES Journal of Marine Science* 75, 1166–1168.
<https://doi.org/10.1093/icesjms/fsx059>
- Thibaut, T., Blanfuné, A., Boudouresque, C.F., Personnic, S., Ruitton, S., Ballesteros, E., Bellan-Santini, D., Bianchi, C.N., Bussotti, S., Cebrian, E., Cheminée, A., Culioli, J.-M., Derrien-Courtel, S., Guidetti, P., Harmelin-Vivien, M., Hereu, B., Morri, C., Poggiale, J.-C., Verlaque, M., 2017. An ecosystem-based approach to assess the status of Mediterranean algae-dominated shallow rocky reefs. *Marine Pollution Bulletin* 117, 311–329. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2017.01.029>
- Thompson, M., 2008. Fostering sustainable behaviours in community-based co-managed fisheries. *Marine Policy* 32, 413–420.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2007.08.005>
- Urquhart, J., Acott, T., Symes, D., Zhao, M., 2014. Introduction: Social issues in sustainable fisheries management, in: Urquhart, J., Acott, T., Symes, D., Zhao, M. (Eds.), . Springer Netherlands, Dordrecht, pp. 1–21. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-007-7911-2_1
- Van Poorten, B., Cox, S., Cooper, A., 2013. Efficacy of harvest and minimum size limit regulations for controlling short-term harvest in recreational fisheries. *Fisheries Management and Ecology* 20, 258–267. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2400.2012.00872.x>
- Williams, I.D., White, D.J., Sparks, R.T., Lino, K.C., Zamzow, J.P., Kelly, E.L.A., Ramey, H.L., 2016. Responses of Herbivorous Fishes and Benthos to 6 Years of Protection at the Kahekili Herbivore Fisheries Management Area, Maui. *PLOS*

ONE 11, e0159100. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0159100>
Zupan, M., Fragkopoulou, E., Claudet, J., Erzini, K., Horta e Costa, B., Gonçalves, E., 2018.
Marine partially protected areas: drivers of ecological effectiveness. *Frontiers in Ecology and the Environment* 16. <https://doi.org/10.1002/fee.1934>

8. Appendix

Appendix A1 : Study sites - Identification number, site localisation and date on which the field-work was carried out.

Sites	Latitude	Longitude	Date
32	38,939565	1,50902435	6/11/2023
31	38,96310893	1,53241806	6/11/2023
30	38,98316783	1,54647801	6/11/2023
29	38,99036417	1,55675375	6/11/2023
1	38,98261102	1,57935381	6/11/2023
2	38,97661469	1,59422257	6/11/2023
3	39,00118246	1,58781858	6/11/2023
4A	39,02363341	1,60198032	6/11/2023
4B	39,02437558	1,603828797	6/11/2023
5	39,02479734	1,61804923	6/11/2023
26	39,11748439	1,52936466	7/11/2023
25	39,11298859	1,5435517	7/11/2023
24	39,10350071	1,54657785	7/11/2023
23	39,09867731	1,55570629	7/11/2023
22	39,09784562	1,568439727	7/11/2023

21	39,09768803	1,57855069	7/11/2023
20	39,10104269	1,59174139	7/11/2023
19	39,09588835	1,59549756	7/11/2023
17	39,08204811	1,60222279	9/11/2023
15	39,07601716	1,60480892	8/11/2023
16A	39,08117381	1,61036251	8/11/2023
16B	39,08070569	1,60961415	8/11/2023
10	39,04586401	1,61386751	8/11/2023
11	39,0495604	1,62000153	8/11/2023
8	39,0365164	1,64765368	8/11/2023
7	39,03194896	1,64582193	8/11/2023
9	39,04081845	1,63601617	8/11/2023
6A	39,03642543	1,62059348	8/11/2023
6B	39,03536307	1,62094233	8/11/2023
14	39,07359429	1,597819179	8/11/2023
28	39,11686015	1,514360644	9/11/2023
27	39,11602038	1,523270485	9/11/2023
18	39,08833171	1,603150415	9/11/2023

13	39,06792633	1,58964539	10/11/2023
12B	39,05485462	1,60234357	10/11/2023
12A	39,0549876	1,60093988	10/11/2023

Appendix A2 : List of observed species, classified by family. English common names are given for each species. Species commonly targeted by fishing are highlighted in gray.

Family	Species Sampled	Common name
Apogonidae	<i>Apogon imberbis</i>	Cardinal fish
Carangidae	<i>Seriola dumerili</i> <i>Pseudocaranx dentex</i>	Greater amberjack White trevally
Epinephelidae	<i>Epinephelus marginatus</i> <i>Epinephelus costae</i> <i>Mycteroperca rubra</i>	Dusky grouper Golden grouper Mottled grouper
Labridae	<i>Coris julis</i> <i>Thalassoma pavo</i> <i>Labrus viridis</i> <i>Labrus merula</i> <i>Symphodus ocellatus</i> <i>Symphodus cinereus</i> <i>Symphodus mediterraneus</i> <i>Symphodus tinca</i> <i>Symphodus roissali</i> <i>Symphodus doderleini</i> <i>Symphodus rostratus</i> <i>Centrolabrus melanocercus</i>	Mediterranean rainbow wrasse Ornate wrasse Green wrasse Brown wrasse Ocellated wrasse Grey wrasse Axillary wrasse East Atlantic peacock wrasse Five-spotted wrasse NA Sublet Black-tailed wrasse
Mugilidae	<i>Mugil</i> sp.	Mullet
Mullidae	<i>Mullus surmuletus</i>	Surmullet
Muraenidae	<i>Muraena helena</i>	Mediterranean moray
Sciaenidae	<i>Sciaena umbra</i>	Brown meagre
Scorpaenidae	<i>Scorpaena notata</i> <i>Scorpaena scrofa</i> <i>Scorpaena maderensis</i>	Small red scorpionfish Red scorpionfish Madeira rockfish

Serranidae	<i>Serranus scriba</i> <i>Serranus cabrilla</i>	<i>Painted comber</i> <i>Comber</i>
Sparidae	<i>Dentex dentex</i> <i>Diplodus annularis</i> <i>Diplodus vulgaris</i> <i>Diplodus puntazzo</i> <i>Diplodus sargus</i> <i>Diplodus cervinus</i> <i>Spondyliosoma cantharus</i> <i>Oblada melanura</i> <i>Sarpa salpa</i> <i>Boops boops</i> <i>Spicara sp.</i>	Common dentex Annular seabream Common two-banded seabream Sharpsnout seabream White seabream Zebra seabream Black seabream Saddled seabream Salema Bogue Picarel
Sphyraenidae	<i>Sphyraena viridensis</i>	Yellowmouth barracuda
Pomacentridae	<i>Chromis chromis</i>	Damselfish

Appendix A3 : List of Mediterranean species most commonly targeted by small scale fisheries, classified by family. English common names are given for each species.

Family	Species Sampled	Common name
Labridae	<i>Coris julis</i> <i>Labrus merula</i> <i>Labrus viridis</i>	Mediterranean rainbow wrasse Brown wrasse Green wrasse
Mugilidae	<i>Mugil sp.</i>	Mullet
Mullidae	<i>Mullus surmuletus</i>	Surmullet
Serranidae	<i>Serranus scriba</i>	Painted comber
Sparidae	<i>Dentex dentex</i> <i>Diplodus annularis</i> <i>Diplodus vulgaris</i> <i>Diplodus puntazzo</i> <i>Diplodus sargus</i> <i>Oblada melanura</i> <i>Pagellus erythrinus</i> <i>Pagrus pagrus</i> <i>Sarpa salpa</i>	Common dentex Annular seabream Common two-banded seabream Sharpsnout seabream White seabream Saddled seabream Common pandora Red porgy Salema